

An Analytic Solution of the Nonlinear Differential Equation

$$\Delta \lambda = f(\lambda)$$

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A spherically symmetric solution of the equation $\Delta \lambda = f(\lambda)$ with the boundary conditions $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ and $(d\lambda/dr)_{r=a} = a$ given value, has been obtained under the assumptions that $f(\lambda)$ is monotonic and can be expanded in a power series about $\lambda=0$ and $f(0)=0$. The series solution $\lambda = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \alpha^s b_s(r) \cdot r^{-1}$, where α is a parameter independent of r ; $b_1 = A \exp(-Kr)$; $K^2 = f'(0)$; $b_s = K^{-1} \int_r^{\infty} G_s(x) \sinh K(x-r) dx$; $G_s = (r/s!) \cdot \delta^s / \delta \alpha^s [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \alpha = 0$, has been proved to be regular in the domain $r > 0$. A solution in the form of an integral equation, namely, $r\lambda(r) = B \exp(-Kr) + K^{-1} \int_r^{\infty} x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \sinh K(x-r) dx$ has also been derived. Using the integral equation and the series solution the values of $\lambda(r)$ have been calculated for the particular case $\Delta \lambda = K^2 [\exp(w\lambda) - \exp(-z\lambda)] / (z+w)$; (K^2, w, z are known real constants).

All the graphs $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a calculated for this case are similar in shape and tend to zero like the function $\exp(-Kr)/r$. The values of λ at $r=a$ for different values of the parameter Ka were found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained by Guggenheim who used a numerical method, but showed significant deviations from those reported by Gronwall who used the first three terms of another series solution.

The equation $\Delta \lambda = f(\lambda)$. . (1) includes the important type of equation known as the Poisson-Boltzmann equation. No explicit general solution of this equation is known. Bagchi, Das and Chakravarti¹ had obtained a spherically symmetric solution in the form of a series as well as in the form of an integral equation of the above equation, i.e., of the equation

$$\frac{d^2 \lambda}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} = f(\lambda) \quad \dots \dots \dots (1a)$$

for $r \gg a$ with the boundary conditions

$$\lambda \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty ; \left(\frac{d\lambda}{dr} \right)_{r=a} = C \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

and under the assumptions that $f(\lambda)$ is monotonic and can be expanded in a power series about $\lambda=0$ and $f(0)=0$. The existence and uniqueness of the solution of (1a) under the boundary conditions (2) and the above assumptions on $f(\lambda)$ were proved by Gronwall². Moreover, Gronwall, LaMer and Sandved³ found an explicit analytic solution under the same boundary conditions for the particular equation⁴

$$\frac{d^2 \lambda}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} = \frac{4 \pi \epsilon^2}{DkT} \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{N n_j z_j}{V} \exp(-z_j \lambda) \quad \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

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1. S. N. Bagchi, G. P. Das, and S. Chakravarti, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Sci. India*, 1961, No. 29, p. 28.
2. T. H. Gronwall, *Ann. Math.* 1927, **28**, 355.
3. T. H. Gronwall, V. K. La Mer, and K. Sandved, *Phys. Z.*, 1928 **29**, 358.
4. V = volume of the solution containing n_j moles of ions of the j^{th} kind of valency z_j ;
 N = Avogadro's number; ϵ = electronic charge;
 k = Boltzmann's constant; T = absolute temperature;
 D = dielectric constant of the medium,

obtained from the Debye-Hueckel theory of strong electrolytes⁵. Although Gronwall *et al.* could not prove the overall convergence of their series solution, it is likely that the solution converges throughout the domain of interest. The main drawback of their solution lies in the fact that it converges slowly and it is extremely laborious to calculate satisfactory results. In view of the importance of the equation (3) Guggenheim⁶ obtained a few accurate values of λ for this equation (for the case of binary electrolytes) using a numerical method proposed by Mueller⁷. In this work we shall prove the convergence of the solution obtained by Bagchi *et al.*¹ and evaluate λ for the particular case where $f(\lambda)$ is given by the right hand side of the equation (3) for the case of binary electrolytes. We shall compare our results with those obtained by Gronwall and by Guggenheim.

Mathematicians have studied the equation $\Delta\lambda=f(\lambda)$ without boundary conditions, but their main interest has been to discover the growth conditions on $f(\lambda)$ which would ensure the existence of an entire solution. Keller⁸ generalized the previous work of other mathematicians on this topic. In the case of a spherically symmetric λ , Keller found necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of an entire solution⁹. A sufficient condition is $f(\lambda_1)=0$ for $\lambda=\lambda_1$, (say), a property assumed by Bagchi *et al.*¹. Nevertheless, due to the boundary conditions (2) our solution is not an entire solution. As proved below the solution has a singularity at $r=0$ and converges uniformly for $r > r_0 > 0$.

I. *The Solution*

Our problem is to find a solution of the equation (1a) for $r \gg a$ under the boundary conditions (2). According to our assumption $f(\lambda)$ is given by

$$f(\lambda) = f'(0)\lambda + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}\lambda^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}\lambda^3 + \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

For the problems of our interest, we assume that $f'(0)=K^2$, a positive real quantity .. (5)

Let us introduce a function $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ depending on the parameter α , independent of r , so that for any fixed value of α , (say α_1), $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ becomes a function of r only which may be denoted by $\lambda_{\alpha_1}(r)$. Since the differential operator acts on r only, $\lambda(r, \alpha)$, $\lambda_{\alpha_1}(r)$ and $\lambda(r)$ all satisfy the same differential equation (1a). First we shall find the solution of this differential equation for a given value of α , (say α_0), determined by the given boundary conditions, i.e., the solution $\lambda_{\alpha_0}(r)$. Let the required solution be given by a power series in α , a parameter independent of r , such that

$$\lambda = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \alpha^s b_s(r) \cdot r^{-1} \dots \dots (6)$$

From (1), (4) and (5) we get

$$\frac{d^2(r\lambda)}{dr^2} - K^2 r \lambda = r [f(\lambda) - K^2\lambda] \dots \dots (7)$$

5. P. Debye, and E. Hueckel, 1923, *Phys. Z.* **24**, 185.
 6. E. A. Guggenheim, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 1714.
 7. H. Mueller, *Phys. Z.* 1927, **28**, 324.
 8. J. B. Keller, *Commun. Pure Appl. Math.* 1957 **10**, 503.
 9. According to Keller eq. (1) has an entire spherically symmetric solution if and only if one of the following conditions is satisfied:

- (i) $f(\lambda_1)=0$; (ii) $f(\lambda) > 0$ and $\int_{\lambda_0}^{\infty} F^{-1/2}(z) dz = \infty$
- (iii) $f(\lambda) < 0$ and $\int_{-\infty}^{\lambda_0} F^{-1/2}(z) dz = \infty$; $[F(z) = \int_{\lambda_0}^z f(t)dt]$

Substituting the value of $r \lambda$ from (6) and expanding the right hand side of (7) in powers of α , we obtain

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \alpha^s [b_s''(r) - K^2 b_s(r)] = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \alpha^s G_s(r) \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} G_1 &= 0 \\ G_2 &= \frac{f''(0)}{2!} \frac{b_1^2}{r} \\ G_s &= \left(\frac{r}{s!} \right) \frac{\delta^s}{\delta \alpha^s} \cdot \left[f \left(\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^s b_s}{r} \right) - K^2 \left(\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^s b_s}{r} \right) \right]_{\alpha=0} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots \quad (9)$$

The eq. (7) is the same as the original differential equation (1a) and is valid for *any fixed* value of α and consequently, eq. (8) is an identity within its domain of convergence. Hence, eq. (10) is valid generally. The unique solution would be obtained for a particular value of α , (say α_0), by imposing subsequently the boundary conditions. (For convenience, we shall write $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ as λ , noting carefully again, in order to avoid any confusion, that any value of $\lambda(r)$ so determined would necessarily depend on the particular value of $\alpha = \alpha_0$ (say) satisfying the boundary conditions.)

Now equating coefficients of α^s on both sides of equation (8) we get a system of differential equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_1'' - K^2 b_1 &= 0 \\ b_s'' - K^2 b_s &= G_s(r), \text{ for } s \gg 2 \end{aligned} \right\} \dots \quad (10)$$

The solutions of (10) are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_1 &= A \exp(-Kr) ; \\ b_s &= K^{-1} \int_r^{\infty} G_s(x) \sinh K(x-r) dx; (s \gg 2) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots \quad (11)$$

Of the two integration constants one vanishes due to the first boundary condition and the other, A, can be determined from the second boundary condition.

From (6), (7), (8), and (11) we get

$$\lambda = r^{-1} \alpha A \exp(-Kr) + (Kr)^{-1} \cdot \int_r^{\infty} x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \sinh K(x-r) dx \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} &= -r^{-2} \alpha A (1+Kr) \exp(-Kr) \\ &\quad - (1+Kr) (Kr^2)^{-1} \int_r^{\infty} x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \sinh K(x-r) dx \\ &\quad - r^{-1} \exp(Kr) \int_r^{\infty} x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \exp(-Kx) dx \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

Hence from (2) we have, at $r=a$,

$$\lambda(a) = -Ca / (1+Ka) - \exp(Ka)/(1+Ka) \cdot \int_a^\infty x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \exp(-Kx) dx$$

$$= \lambda_L - \exp(Ka)/(1+Ka) \cdot \int_a^\infty x [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda] \exp(-Kx) dx \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

where $\lambda_L(a) = -Ca/(1+Ka)$, $\lambda(r) = \frac{Ca^2}{1+Ka} \frac{\exp\{-K(r-a)\}}{r}$ is the solution, of the linearized equation

$$\frac{d^2 \lambda}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} = K^2 \lambda \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

at $r = a$ under the boundary condtions (2).

It must again be explicitly emphasized here that this value of $\lambda(a, \alpha)$ depends on the particular value of $\alpha = \alpha_0$ which satisfies the given boundary condtions so that α_0 is in fact a function of C . We shall prove later that such a value exists. Now the value of $\lambda(r)$ at any point $r > a$ can be expressed in terms of $\lambda(a)$ as

$$\lambda(r) = X_1(r) \lambda(a) + X_2(r) \lambda^2(a) + \dots \quad (16)$$

Since $\lambda(r) = \alpha b_1(r) r^{-1} + \alpha^2 b_2(r) \cdot r^{-1} + \dots$

and $X_n \lambda^n(a) = X_n [\alpha b_1(a) \cdot a^{-1} + \alpha^2 b_2(a) \cdot a^{-1} + \dots]^n \dots \quad (17)$

one can, by equating the coefficients of equal powers of α in (16), obtain X_n in terms of b_{j+1} and X_j , ($j \leq n-1$).

To evaluate the numerical value of $\lambda(r)$ for the particular value of $\alpha = \alpha_0$, one calculates first $\lambda(a)$, which also depends on the same value of $\alpha = \alpha_0$, by Horner's and Simpson's methods and then $\lambda(r)$ with the help of eqs. (16) and (17). A closer inspection of this perturbation series with the help of the majorant series (6a) (see page 7) would show immediately that the series (16) converges uniformly and absolutely. Since we are using the methods of numerical computation to determine $\lambda(a)$ and the perturbation technique to express $\lambda(r)$ in powers of $\lambda(a)$, for evaluating the value of $\lambda(r)$ we do not need to know exactly the value of α_0 . But for this numerical calculation it is necessary to calculate the first few terms of the functions $G_s(r)$, $b_s(r)$ and $X_s(r)$. Tables I to III give these terms up to $s=7$.

TABLE I

The expressions for G_s

$$G_3 = (r/s!) \delta^3 / \delta a^3 [f(\lambda) - K^2 \lambda]_{a=0} = (r/s!) \delta / \delta a^2 \left[\frac{f''(0)}{2!} \lambda^2 + \frac{f^{(3)}(0)}{3!} \lambda^3 + \dots \right]_{a=0}$$

The general term can be obtained from the multinomial expression

$$(r/s!) \delta^s / \delta a^s [f^{(n)}(0) / (n!) \cdot (r^{-1} b_1 a + r^{-1} b_2 a^2 + r^{-1} b_3 a^3 + \dots)^n] = (r/s!) \delta^s / \delta a^s [f^{(n)}(0) / (n!) \{(n!)_1 / (a_1! a_2! \dots (b_1^{a_1} b_2^{a_2} \dots)) / (r^{a_1 + a_2 + \dots}) a^{a_1 + 2a_2 + 3a_3 + \dots}\} \alpha = 0$$

TABLE I (contd.)

where $a_1 + a_2 + \dots + n$; $a_1 + 2a_2 + \dots = s$, if we note that only the coefficient of x^s contributes to G_s . Since n can vary from 2 to s , we have

$$G_s(r) = r \sum \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!} \frac{n!}{a_1! \dots a_{s-1}!} \left(\frac{b_1}{r}\right)^{a_1} \dots \left(\frac{b_{s-1}}{r}\right)^{a_{s-1}}$$

summed over all permissible values of $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{s-1}$

In particular

$$G_1(r) = 0$$

$$G_2(r) = f''(0)/(2!) \cdot r^{-1} b_1^2(r)$$

$$G_3(r) = f^{(3)}(0)/(3!) \cdot r^{-2} b_1^3 + f''(0)/(1!) \cdot r^{-1} b_1 b_2$$

$$G_4(r) = f^{(4)}(0)/(4!) \cdot r^{-3} b_1^4 + f^{(3)}(0)/(2!) \cdot r^{-2} b_1^2 b_2 + f''(0)/(2!) \cdot (r^{-1} b_2^2 + 2! r^{-1} b_1 b_3)$$

$$G_5(r) = f^{(5)}(0)/(5!) \cdot r^{-4} b_1^5 + f^{(4)}(0)/(3!) \cdot r^{-3} b_1^3 b_2 + f^{(3)}(0)/(2!) \cdot (r^{-2} b_1 b_2^2 + r^{-2} b_1^2 b_3) + f''(0)/(1!) \cdot (r^{-1} b_2 b_3 + r^{-1} b_1 b_4)$$

$$G_6(r) = f^{(6)}(0)/(6!) \cdot r^{-5} b_1^6 + f^{(5)}(0)/(4!) \cdot r^{-4} b_1^4 b_2 + f^{(4)}(0) \cdot r^{-3} [b_1^2 b_2^2 / (2!)(2!) + b_1^3 b_3 / (3!)] + f^{(3)}(0) \cdot r^{-2} [b_1 b_2 b_3 + b_1^2 b_4 / (2!) + b_2^3 / (3!)] + f''(0) r^{-1} [b_1 b_3 + b_2 b_4 + b_3^2 / (2!)]$$

$$G_7(r) = f^{(7)}(0)/(7!) \cdot r^{-6} b_1^7 + f^{(6)}(0)/(5!) \cdot r^{-5} b_1^5 b_2 + f^{(5)}(0)/(4!) \cdot r^{-4} [2! b_1^3 b_2^2 + b_1^4 b_3] + f^{(4)}(0) \cdot r^{-3} [b_1 b_2^3 / (3!) + b_1^2 b_2 b_3 / (2!) + b_1^3 b_4 / (3!)] + f^{(3)}(0)/(2!) \cdot r^{-2} [2! b_1 b_2 b_4 + b_1 b_3^2 + b_2^2 b_3 + b_1 b_5] + f''(0) \cdot r^{-1} (b_1 b_6 + b_2 b_3 + b_3 b_4)$$

TABLE II

The expressions for b_s

$$b_1(r) = A \exp(-Kr)$$

$$b_2(r) = f''(0)/(2!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-1} \cdot b_1^2(x) \sinh K(x-r) dx$$

$$b_3(r) = f^{(3)}(0)/(3!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-2} b_1^3(x) \sinh K(x-r) dx + f''(0)/(2!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-1} b_1(x) b_2(x) \sinh K(x-r) dx$$

$$b_4(r) = f^{(4)}(0)/(4!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-3} b_1^4 \sinh K(x-r) dx + f^{(3)}(0)/(2!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-2} b_1^2 b_2 \sinh K(x-r) dx + f''(0)/(2!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty [x^{-1} b_2^2 + 2x^{-1} b_1 b_3] \sinh K(x-r) dx$$

$$b_5(r) = f^{(5)}(0)/(5!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-4} b_1^5 \sinh K(x-r) dx + f^{(4)}(0)/(3!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x^{-3} b_1^3 b_2 \sinh K(x-r) dx + f^{(3)}(0)/(2!) \cdot K^{-1} \int_r^\infty [x^{-2} b_1 b_2^2 + x^{-2} b_1^2 b_3] \sinh K(x-r) dx + f''(0) K^{-1} \int_r^\infty [x^{-1} b_2 b_3 + x^{-1} b_1 b_4] \sinh K(x-r) dx$$

$$b_6(r) = K^{-1} \int_r^\infty [f^{(6)}(0)/(6!) \cdot x^{-5} b_1^6 + f^{(5)}(0)/(4!) \cdot x^{-4} b_1^4 b_2 + f^{(4)}(0) x^{-3} \{b_1^2 b_2^2 / (2!)(2!) + b_1^3 b_3 / (3!)\}] + f^{(3)}(0) x^{-2} \{b_1 b_2 b_3 + b_1^2 b_4 / (2!) + b_2^3 / (3!)\} + f''(0) x^{-1} [b_1 b_3 + b_2 b_4 + b_3^2 / (2!)] \cdot \sinh K(x-r) dx$$

$$b_7(r) = K^{-1} \int_r^\infty [f^{(7)}(0)/(7!) \cdot x^{-6} b_1^7 + f^{(6)}(0)/(5!) \cdot x^{-5} b_1^5 b_2$$

TABLE II (contd.)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ f^{(5)}(0). x^{-4} \{2! b_1^3 b_2^2 / (4!) + b_1^4 b_3 / (4!)\} \\
 &+ f^{(4)}(0). x^{-3} \{b_1 b_2^3 / (3!) + b_1^2 b_2 b_3 / (2!) + b_1^3 b_4 / (3!)\} \\
 &+ f^{(3)}(0). x^{-2} \{b_1 b_2 b_4 / (1!) + b_1 b_3^2 / (2!) + b_2^2 b_3 / (2!) + b_1^2 b_5 / (2!)\} \\
 &+ f''(0) x^{-1} \{b_1 b_6 + b_2 b_5 + b_3 b_4\} \sinh K(x-r) dx
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE III

The expressions for X_s

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_1(r) &= a. r^{-1} \exp [-K(r-a)] \\
 X_2(r) &= a^2. \exp (2Ka) \{r^{-1} b_2(r) - X_1(r). a^{-1} b_2(a)\} \\
 X_3(r) &= a_3. \exp (3Ka) \{r^{-1} b_3(r) - X_1(r). a^{-1} b_3(a)\} - 2a X_2(r) b_2(a) \exp (2Ka) \\
 X_4(r) &= a^4. \exp (4Ka) \{r^{-1} b_4(r) - X_1(r). a^{-1} b_4(a)\} \\
 &\quad - a^2 X_2(r) \exp (4Ka) \{b_2^2(a) + 2b_1(a) b_3(a)\} - 3a X_3(r) b_2(a) \exp (2Ka) \\
 X_5(r) &= a^5. \exp (5Ka) \cdot \{r^{-1} b_5(r) - X_1(r). a^{-1} b_5(a)\} - 4a X_4(r) b_2(a) \exp (2Ka) \\
 &\quad - 3a^2. X_3(r) \{ \exp (4Ka). b_2^2(a) + \exp (3Ka) b_3(a) \} \\
 &\quad - 2a^3 X_2(r) \{ \exp (4Ka) b_4(a) + \exp (5Ka) b_2(a) b_3(a) \} \\
 X_6(r) &= a^6. \exp (6Ka) \{r^{-1} b_6(r) - X_1(r) a^{-1} b_6(a)\} \\
 &\quad - a^4. X_2(r) \exp (6Ka) \{b_3^2(a) + 2b_1(a) b_5(a) + 2b_2(a). b_4(a)\} \\
 &\quad - a^3. X_3(r) \exp (6Ka) \{b_2^2(a) + 3b_1^2(a) b_4(a) + 6b_1(a) b_2(a) b_3(a)\} \\
 &\quad - a^2 X_4(r) \exp (6Ka) \{6b_1^2(a) b_2^2(a) + 4b_1^3(a) b_3(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 5a X_5(r) \exp (6Ka) \cdot \{b_1^4(a) b_2(a)\} \\
 X_7(r) &= a^7. \exp (7Ka) \{r^{-1} b_1(r) - X_1(r) a^{-1} b_7(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 6a X_6(r) \exp (7Ka). \{b_1^5(a). b_2(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 5a^2 X_5(r) \exp (7Ka). \{b_1^4(a) b_3(a) + 2b_1^2(a) b_2^2(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 4a^3 X_4(r) \exp (7Ka). \{b_1^3 a b_4(a) + b_1(a) b_2^3(a) + 3b_1^2(a) b_2(a) b_3(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 3a^2 X_3(r) \exp (7Ka). \{b_1^2(a) b_5(a) + b_2^2(a). b_3(a) \\
 &\quad + b_3^2(a) b_1(a) + 2b_1(a) b_2(a) b_4(a)\} \\
 &\quad - 2a^5 X_2(r) \exp (7Ka). \{b_1(a) b_6(a) + b_2(a) b_5(a) + b_3(a) b_4(a)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

II. Convergence

From eq. (11) and the expressions in Tables I and II it is easily proved that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left| \frac{b_s}{r} \right| &= \frac{1}{K} \int_r^\infty \Sigma \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{a_1! \dots a_{s-1}!} \left(\frac{b_1}{x} \right)^{a_1} \dots \left(\frac{b_{s-1}}{x} \right)^{a_{s-1}} \sinh K(x-r) dx \\
 &\leq \frac{\beta^s}{(s+1)(s-1)} \Sigma \frac{A^n f^{(n)}(0)}{K^2} \cdot \frac{1}{a_1! \dots a_{s-1}!} \left(\frac{1}{D_1} \right)^{a_1} \dots \left(\frac{1}{D_{s-1}} \right)^{a_{s-1}} \\
 &\leq \frac{\beta^s}{(s+1)(s-1)} \Sigma \frac{1}{a_1! \dots a_{s-1}!} \left(\frac{1}{D_1} \right)^{a_1} \dots \left(\frac{1}{D_{s-1}} \right)^{a_{s-1}} \dots \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

if we choose the integration constant A in such a way that $\frac{A^n f^{(n)}(0)}{K^2} \leq 1$.

D_s^{-1} is the proportionality constant in the relation

$$\left| \frac{b_s}{r} \right| \leq \frac{e^{-sKr}}{D_s \cdot r^s} = \frac{\beta^s}{D_s}, \quad \left(\beta = \frac{e^{-Kr}}{r} \right).$$

The summation is to be taken over all the values of a_s consistent with

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_1 + 2a_2 + \dots + (s-1) a_{s-1} &= s \\
 a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_{s-1} &= n; \quad (n \text{ varies from } s \text{ to } 2).
 \end{aligned}$$

Exact evaluation of $|b_s/r|$ from $s=1$ to 20 shows that the coefficient $1/D_s$ decreases quite rapidly with increasing s , but for the proof of the convergence it would be sufficient if we take as a rough majorant of the series (6), the series

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^s \beta^s}{s} \dots \dots \dots (6a)$$

First, we prove by the method of induction that if

$$\left| \frac{b_s}{r} \right| \geq \frac{\beta^s}{s}, \text{ then } \left| \frac{b_{s+1}}{r} \right| \leq \frac{\beta^{s+1}}{(s+1)}$$

From (18) it follows

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{b_{s+1}}{r} \right| &\leq \frac{\beta^{s+1}}{(s+2)s} \sum \frac{1}{a_1! \dots a_s!} \left(\frac{1}{1}\right)^{a_1} \dots \dots \dots \left(\frac{1}{s}\right)^{a_s} \\ &= \frac{\beta^{s+1}}{(s+2)s} \\ &< \frac{\beta^{s+1}}{(s+1)}, \end{aligned}$$

since¹⁰

$$\sum \frac{1}{a_1! \dots a_s! (1)^{a_1} \dots (s)^{a_s}} = 1,$$

the summation being over all values of $a_1, \dots, a_s$ such that $a_1 + 2a_2 + \dots + sa_s = (s+1)$.

Hence the series (6a), and, consequently also the series (6), converge uniformly and absolutely for $r \gg a > 0$ if we choose α in such a way that the inequality

$$\frac{\exp - Ka \cdot \alpha}{a} < 1 \dots \dots \dots (19)$$

holds.

Now we have only to show that for any value of α given by (19) we can satisfy the boundary condition $d\lambda/dr |_{r=a} = C$. This is evident from the fact that both the power series λ and $d\lambda/dr |_{r=a}$ having the same radius of convergence are continuous functions and increase from 0 (for $\alpha=0$) to α (for $\alpha \geq R=a \exp Ka$, the radius of convergence). By inspecting the majorant series (6a) one can verify easily that the series $d\lambda/dr |_{r=a}$ also converges uniformly and absolutely.

Before proceeding to the actual evaluation of $\lambda(r)$ it would perhaps not be out of place here to pass a few remarks about the solution obtained by introducing an arbitrary parameter.

The equation (6) expresses $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ in power series of α and consequently in its domain of convergence it is an analytic function of α . But for any fixed value of α , satisfying the relation $\alpha < a \exp (Ka)$ it becomes a series of functions of r which is

10. This relation has been proved by Jacobi (1841) and by Sylvester (1861). See History of The Theory of Numbers by L. E. Dickson, Vol 11, pp.124, 143. Chelsea Publishing Co. New York, 1952.

also absolutely and uniformly convergent for $r \geq a > 0$. Therefore, for any such value of α (say α_0), $\lambda(r, \alpha_0) \equiv \lambda_{\alpha_0}(r)$ is an analytic function of r , although in eq. (6) it is not expressed explicitly and directly in power series of r . It is also evident from the majorant series (6a) that the series (6) being absolutely convergent for $r \geq a > 0$ and $\alpha < a \exp(Ka)$, one can express $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ in powers of r by rearranging the terms. Consequently, $\lambda(r, \alpha)$ is an analytic function both of α and of r .

Further, since $d\lambda/dr$ is a continuous function whose value can vary from 0 to ∞ by choosing the value of α properly, one can always find the value of α for any value of C given by physical conditions. Hence although the eq. (14) has been proved valid only for the particular value of the parameter α_0 determined from the given value of C , but since one can vary C continuously, the eq. (14) would remain valid for any value of C . That means, eqs. (12) and (14) are generally satisfied irrespective of the value of α as long as the series (6) is absolutely convergent. This is further confirmed by the fact that the integral equation,

$$r\lambda(r) = B \exp(-Kr) + K^{-1} \int_r^\infty x [f(\lambda(r)) - K^2 \lambda(r)] \sinh K(x-r) dx \quad (12),$$

(B is any arbitrary

constant to be determined from the boundary conditions), is completely equivalent to the differential equation (7) i.e., with the eq (1a). This can be verified in many ways, for example,

(i) by its direct differentiation

(ii) by constructing a fundamental solution from the equation —

$$\frac{d^2}{dr^2} Y - K^2 Y = \delta(x-0)$$

so that $r\lambda = Y * \Psi$; $\left[\Psi(r) = r \{f(\lambda(r)) - K^2 \lambda(r)\} \right]$
 [*denotes convolution product]

In fact, Gronwall *et al.*³ obtained a very similar integral equation for the differential equation (3) by constructing the Green's function ζ (in the usual sense) with the boundary conditions $\zeta \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ and $d\zeta/dr|_{r=a} = 0$.

Consequently, the integral equations (12) and (14) do not depend on the arbitrary parameter used in the series solution. Since in the actual evaluation of $\lambda(r)$ we have used the integral equations (12) and (14), one might pertinently ask why we have taken the trouble of obtaining a cumbersome series solution at all. Superficially, it might appear that the entire procedure with the series solution is redundant. But a careful examination of the usual method of solution of the nonlinear integral equation shows that at one stage one must use a series expansion. We did this with the eq. (14) and not directly with the eq. (12) for convenience of calculation and consequently we had to use the perturbation technique to obtain $\lambda(r)$. Everywhere again one needs a series expansion. A careful study of Gronwall *et al.*'s work³ would show that expanding $\lambda(r)$ in inverse powers of the dielectric constant, which appears also as a parameter in $f(\lambda)$ for the particular case they solved, leads to an unsatisfactory convergent series. Since the series (6), which expresses the complete potential $\lambda(r)$ in powers of the Debye (or Yukawa) potential, was found to be a *practical*

necessity to tackle many physical and physico-chemical problems, as will be shown in future communications, we used this series in expanding $\lambda(r)$. Consequently, for this as well as for subsequent work where the perturbation technique is used by terminating this series at a suitable point, it is necessary to prove satisfactorily the difficult task that the series (6) converges uniformly and absolutely and determine its domain as well as the radius of convergence. Further, with the help of the majorant series (6a) one can easily verify that the integral equation (12) also converges uniformly and absolutely. Of course, one could assert that since this integral equation is completely equivalent to the differential equation (1a) and since it has been proved that the differential equation with the boundary conditions gives unique analytic solution, the corresponding integral equation also furnishes the same unique analytic solution. Nevertheless, a direct and independent proof of the convergence of the nonlinear integral equation is desirable in many cases. These are the justifications for introducing the series with a parameter independent of r . Further, it also gave rise to an equivalent integral equation and to the fundamental solution of the differential operator. A little exercise would convince anyone that such results could not be arrived at, at least not so easily as here, if one at the outset started with a power series of r or of the function

$$\beta = \exp (-Kr)/r.$$

Finally, it might be noted that since for calculating important physical and physico-chemical properties of systems a functional relation of $\lambda(r)$, even if it be an approximate relation, instead of the exact numerical value of $\lambda(r)$, is necessary, it might be more advantageous in many cases (as will be shown in later communications) to use a few terms of this series solution and determine α from the boundary conditions instead of the more exact but far more laborious processes of calculating $\lambda(a)$ first from eq. (14) and the $\lambda(r)$ from eqs. (16) and (17). Here we have, nevertheless, carried out the latter more tedious operations in order to show convincingly that the method and the solution proposed here lead to very accurate results by comparing them with 100% computer solution.

III. Numerical Evaluation of $\lambda(a)$ and $\lambda(r)$ for the Equation (3)

This equation is encountered in the Debye-Hueckel theory of strong electrolytes and determines the potential Ψ at a distance r from a central ion where $\lambda = \epsilon\Psi/kT$. If for a negative central ion we determine $-\lambda$ instead of λ we get for all two component electrolytes

$$f(\lambda) = K^2 \cdot [\exp(w\lambda) - \exp(-z\lambda)] / (z+w);$$

$$K^2 = \frac{4 \pi \nu z (z+w) \epsilon^2 c}{DkT} \quad (20)$$

z and w are the magnitudes of the charges of the central and the opposite ion in the atmosphere in units of the electronic charge ϵ ; ν = number of central ions per molecule of the solute, c = molecular concentration. We have calculated the values of $\lambda(a)$ for the particular case where $f(\lambda)$ is given by the equation (20) and for the values of the dimensionless parameter Ka , ($a = 4.08 \text{ \AA}$), given by Guggenheim⁶. The reported values of Gronwall have also been taken from the above paper of Guggenheim.

The value of $\lambda(a)$ is given by the equation (14). To evaluate the integral numerically, the expression (16) for $\lambda(x)$ is terminated at a suitable point and then inserted in (14). The integral is then evaluated by Simpson's rule:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_{2n}} y dx = h/3 \cdot [y_0 + y_{2n} + T_n + S_n]$$

where

.. (21)

$$T_n = 4 \sum_{i=1}^n y_{2i-1}; \quad S_n = 2 \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} y_{2i}$$

and $h =$ distance between points on the abscissa.

This gives a relation

$$\lambda(a) = \lambda_L(a) + H(\lambda(a)) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

Where $H(\lambda(a))$ is a known function of $\lambda(a)$ resulting from (21) and (16). $\lambda(a)$ is then determined from (22) by Horner's method. Once $\lambda(a)$ is found, the value of λ at any point is obtained from (16) by again terminating the series at a suitable point. The results shown below have been obtained from an I.B.M. 1620 and for larger values of X_n , an I. B. M. 7040¹¹. There are two sources of error in the numerical calculation. One comes from the integration in steps of ma to the final value na (instead of up to ∞ in infinitesimal steps) and the other from the termination of the series (17). In each case the error was practically eliminated by carrying out the calculation so far that no significant difference in the results up to fourth significant place could be obtained.

IV. Results

Table IV gives λ_L and $-\delta\lambda = \lambda_L - \lambda$ at $r=a$ for 1 - 1 electrolytes for various values of Ka . For comparison the corresponding values of $-\delta\lambda$ obtained by Gronwall *et al.* [third column, $-\delta\lambda$ (Gr.)] as quoted by Guggenheim and those obtained by Guggenheim⁶ [fourth column, $-\delta\lambda$ (Gu)] have also been included. Our values are in good agreement with theirs.

Tables V, VI, VII give the corresponding results for 2-2, 1 - 2, and 2 - 1 electrolytes. Again our values are in good agreement with those of Guggenheim, but in the case of 2 - 2 and 2 - 1 electrolytes they differ markedly from those reported by Gronwall. Presumably, this was due to the fact that in the calculation only three terms of the Gronwall's series solution was taken into account. In our case for 1 - 1 and 1 - 2 electrolytes it was found sufficient to take the terms involving X_1 , X_2 and X_3 , in the equation (16) in the numerical integration, but for 2 - 2 and 2 - 1 electrolytes the terms involving X_4 and X_5 also had to be used. In all cases integration up to $r=9a$ gave satisfactory results but as a check in many cases we carried out the integration up to $27a$. In the case of 1 - 1 and 1 - 2 electrolytes integration was carried out in steps of $0.1a$ and in other cases the steps of $0.05a$ were taken.

11. Our thanks are due to the Director of the Computing Centre, McGill University, Montreal, for kindly granting us facilities for using this machine.

TABLE IV

Comparison of our values of λ at $r=a$ with those of Gronwall and Guggenheim for 1 — 1 electrolytes.

Ka	λL	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gr})$	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gu})$	$-\delta\lambda$
1.00	.8750	.0096	.0096	.0096
.95	.8974	.0100	.0100	.0100
.90	.9211	.0104	.0104	.0104
.85	.9459	.0107	.0107	.0107
.80	.9722	.0110	.0110	.0110
.75	1.000	.0113	.0113	.0113
.70	1.029	.0116	.0116	.0116
.65	1.061	.0119	.0118	.0119
.60	1.094	.0120	.0121	.0121
.55	1.129	.0121	.0122	.0122
.50	1.167	.0122	.0122	.0122
.45	1.207	.0122	.0122	.0121
.40	1.250	.0119	.0118	.0118
.35	1.296	.0113	.0113	.0113
.30	1.346	.0106	.0106	.0106
.25	1.400	.0094	.0095	.0095
.20	1.458	.0079	.0081	.0080
.15	1.522	.0060	.0061	.0060
.10	1.591	.0037	.0037	.0037
.05	1.667	.0014	.0014	.0014

TABLE V

Comparison of our values of λ at $r=a$ with those of Gronwall and Guggenheim for 2 — 2 electrolytes

Ka	λL	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gr.})$	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gu})$	$-\delta\lambda$
.40	2.500	.414	.355	.355
.35	2.593	.424	.357	.357
.30	2.692	.424	.355	.354
.25	2.800	.409	.344	.344
.20	2.917	.371	.322	.322
.15	3.043	.303	.282	.281
.10	3.181	.200	.211	.211
.05	3.333	.077	.100	.100

TABLE VI

Comparison of our values of λ at $r=a$ with those of Gronwall and Guggenheim for 1 — 2 electrolytes

Ka	λ_c	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gr.})$	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gu})$	$-\delta\lambda$
.40	1.250	.077	.080	.0811
.35	1.296	.073	.078	.0781
.30	1.346	.068	.074	.0741
.25	1.400	.060	.068	.0675
.20	1.458	.050	.058	.0585
.15	1.522	.037	.046	.0461
.10	1.591	.024	.030	.0296

TABLE VII

Comparison of our values of λ at $r=a$ with those of Gronwall and Guggenheim for 2 — 1 electrolytes

Ka	λ_c	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gr})$	$-\delta\lambda(\text{Gu})$	$-\delta\lambda$
.40	2.500	.052	-.006	-.0067
.35	2.593	.056	-.003	-.0039
.30	2.692	.058	-.001	-.0015
.25	2.800	.057	.000	-.0003
.20	2.917	.051	.000	+ .0002
.15	3.043	.040	-.001	-.0003
.10	3.181	.025	-.002	-.0017
.05	3.333	.008	-.002	-.0023

We have calculated the values of $\lambda(r)$ for all values of Ka mentioned in the tables IV-VII for r going up to $9a$ in steps of .04 or .05. All the graphs of $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a are similar

Fig. 1. $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a for 1-1 electrolytes

Fig. 2. $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a for 2-2 electrolytes

in shape and tend to zero like the function $x^{-1} \exp(-Kx)$. Figures 1 - 4 show the graphs of $\lambda(r)$ plotted as a function of r/a for a few representative values of Ka .

Fig. 3. $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a for 1-3 electrolytes

Fig. 4. $\lambda(r)$ vs. r/a for 2-1 electrolytes

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